

How to talk about data documentation – Are we ready to help researchers?

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Long-term preservation of data requires good documentation

- Metadata is usually poor and insufficient
 - Researchers are self-taught about documentation
- Level of understanding differs

Concepts, words and terms used by data librarians and researchers are different.

What means data documentation?

Documentation is the **process of describing** data

- clarifying structure
- explaining variables used in a data set
- file naming conventions
- etc

Metadata

2001 (11)

How to talk about data documentation with researchers?

Our solution to this problem

1. Documentation guide
2. Documentation expert in data support

2001 (11)

Making a research project understandable

Guide for data documentation

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Documentation check list

We have used for:

- Background material & discussion tool with researchers
- Evaluating of FAIRness of the data set
- How much time & resources needed for improving documentation to FAIR enough level

ELEMENTS OF DATA DOCUMENTATION

Metadata standards & vocabularies

- Describe data in a controlled format using vocabularies
- Use field and disciplinary specific standards, if suitable standards exist
- Should always be favored, if suitable for project

Data management software, i.e. databases and electronic laboratory notebooks

- Software take data in and create a database
- Makes documentation easier as software usually generate metadata by themselves
- Easy to share & control access, usually have safe storage & search tools
- Easy error spotting: inputs out of range can be automatically detected

Data dictionaries

- Dictionaries explain variables used in a dataset
- Codebooks are collections of codes, algorithms and calculations used in a project

Directory structure

- Create a folder structure to suit your project needs
- If you work with sensitive data, a clear folder system helps also in access control
- Balance between shallow and deep folder hierarchy to keep files findable

Tagging files

- Tags are keywords assigned to files, which enable organizing and searching files easier
- A file can only be in one folder at a time, but it may have an unlimited number of tags

File naming conventions

- Create a meaningful but brief system with unique names (in case of directory structure break-down) in the beginning of the project

Version control

- Version control makes it possible to return to an older version of a specific file
- Automatic version control system preferred

Readme-files

- Readme-files are text documents (e.g. format.txt) providing information about data files to ensure they are interpreted correctly
- Readme-files can include information such as title, creator, description, location, methodology, dates and file formats

Discovery metadata

- Descriptive metadata, "label of the dataset", where the dataset is explained should always be published regardless of the nature of the data
- Persistent identifiers (PIDs) identify citable online resources providing a permanent link to them. Persistent identifiers are used when citing and managing data and information

Research records

- Administrative documents (i.e. licenses, usage agreements, consents used) and other research related documents (e.g. research plan, publications, DMP) explaining the context of the actual metadata

Documentation expert in data support

New role would include:

- consultation services
- courses
- develop organisational processes and tools
- cooperate with data archives

Thank you!

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